

Recurrent Neural Network-based NMPC for Nonlinear Processes*

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Abstract—This paper investigates the application of model predictive control (MPC) based on recurrent neural networks (RNNs) in addressing challenges posed by nonlinear process dynamics. The study considers a continuous-flow stirred tank reactor characterized by complex equilibrium series kinetics; informative data generation, model training, and model testing are discussed herein. A comparative analysis with the nominal scenario, based on the first-principles model with no plant/model mismatch, and with some traditional linear data-driven models, highlights the competitive performance of RNN-based MPC in simulated control scenarios. Suitable key performance indicators demonstrate the effectiveness in controlling optimal targets, tracking setpoint variations, and rejecting disturbances. The proposed RNN-based MPC offers a competitive approach to enhance control strategies in complex dynamic nonlinear systems.

Index Terms—Neural networks in process control; Model predictive and optimization-based control; Software for system identification; Subspace methods

I. INTRODUCTION

Implementation of a data-driven model predictive control (MPC) typically involves several key steps crucial for a successful execution: data collection and preprocessing; model identification, prediction horizon, and control inputs; implementation and adaptation [1]. Moreover, the theoretical bases of data-driven MPC relies on machine learning (ML) techniques, such as regression analysis, neural networks (NNs), and statistical learning, to extract patterns, trends, and relationships within the data, enabling predictive models that capture process dynamics [2].

Integrating artificial NNs (ANNs) and control systems has provided robust solutions for various applications. Starting from the foundational contribution to NN training represented by the back-propagation algorithm [3], various architectures and learning methods for ANNs are available and suitable for

specific purposes, i.e., classification, function approximation, data filtering, etc. ANNs are black box systems capable of delivering high performance in applications that require insights from unstructured, high-dimensional data. According to their signal flow, ANNs can be divided into two major categories: Feedforward (FNN) and Recurrent (RNN). In FNN, signals flow from input(s) toward output(s) with no feedback, i.e., each neuron output is connected to the inputs of the next layer of neurons [4]. But in RNN, neurons can receive inputs from any other neuron in the network, regardless of position. A key difference between FNN and RNN is that FNNs are static, producing one output per input, while RNNs are dynamic, allowing the same input to produce varying outputs. FNNs are memoryless, while RNNs can temporarily store information [5]. Therefore, RNNs are better candidates for identifying time-varying systems and coping with situations where time plays a key role, such as time-sequence analysis. Nevertheless, feedback throughout the network adds both dynamics and complexity, requiring stability analysis, although stability is not always guaranteed. Compared to other ML methods, RNNs offer advantages in high scalability and the capacity to model multiple-output data. As RNNs inherently support sequential data modeling, they can well simulate discrete-time dynamical systems, a feature often lacking in other NN variants [6].

Recently, RNNs have gained significant interest across various ML applications, particularly for tasks involving inputs with long time lags, such as speech recognition. Nevertheless, while Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have been widely used across fields, their application in dynamic systems identification and MPC in chemical processes remains a developing area. Since the initial exploration of RNNs for controlling non-linear systems [7], limited research has delved into the integration of these networks with MPC. For instance, applications include control scenarios for reactions in Continuous Stirred Tank Reactors (CSTRs) [8], though the study was confined to

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a relatively simple kinetics, such as single-step irreversible reactions. Later, in [6] and [9] efficient representations and approximations of MPC laws via deep learning were presented, while in [10] a large-scale MPC with structured NNs was developed. More recently, [11] developed a fast explicit ML-based MPC for nonlinear processes using input convex NNs.

In this context, this paper investigates the ability of RNNs to model time-dependent systems, focusing on challenges posed by nonlinear dynamics and including these networks in an established MPC framework. The remainder of the paper is as follows: the integration of RNN with MPC is described in Section II. A CSTR system, characterized by a series equilibrium kinetics, is used in Section III as a significant case of nonlinear dynamic systems. Empirical investigation and comparative analysis with traditional data-driven linear models along with the effectiveness of the RNN-MPC approach in maintaining steady-state conditions, tracking setpoints, and rejecting disturbances are presented in Section IV. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The adopted MPC comprises three key modules (steady-state optimization, dynamic optimization, and disturbance estimator) for effective real-time control of the system. A traditional MPC can be affected by plant/model mismatch or persistent disturbances which impact its performance. To achieve offset-free control, disturbance modeling and estimation are required. Following the approach of [12], an integrating disturbance model is included. The estimator computes the error ($\epsilon_k = y_k - \hat{y}_k$) between the plant output y_k and the model prediction \hat{y}_k at each time k . This error is used to update the disturbance estimate \hat{d} using linear filtering:

$$\hat{d}_k = (1 - K)\hat{d}_{k-1} + K\epsilon_k \quad (1)$$

where $K \in (0, 1)$ is the filter gain to be suitably tuned [13]. The corrected disturbance estimate is fed to both the steady-state and dynamic optimization modules to update the nonlinear model output as follows:

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k) \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{y}_k = h(x_k, u_k) + \hat{d}_k \quad (3)$$

The steady-state optimization module computes the optimal targets for inputs (u_s), states (x_s), and outputs (y_s) to attain a desired steady-state operating point. This implies solving, at each time k , a constrained optimization problem aimed at minimizing an objective function while respecting system bounds and steady-state dynamics as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{u_s, x_s} & \|y_{sp} - y_s\|_{Q_s}^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \\ x_s &= f(x_s, u_s); \quad y_s = h(x_s) + \hat{d}_k \\ u_{min} &\leq u_s \leq u_{max}; \quad y_{min} \leq y_s \leq y_{max} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where y_{sp} is the setpoint, Q_s is the relative weighting matrix, and u_{min} , u_{max} , y_{min} , y_{max} are the input/output constraints.

MPCs typically use an explicit dynamic model to forecast the impact of future manipulated variables on both outputs and

inputs by minimizing a cost function over a set time horizon. The optimal control problem of adopted MPC employs a tracking-type objective function:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{x}} & \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (\|\hat{y}_j - y_s\|_Q^2 + \|u_j - u_s\|_R^2) \\ & + \|\hat{y}_N - y_s\|_{Q_f}^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \\ x_{j+1} &= f(x_j, u_j), \quad j = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ \hat{y}_j &= h(x_j) + \hat{d}_k \quad j = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ u_{min} &\leq u_j \leq u_{max} \quad j = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ y_{min} &\leq \hat{y}_j \leq y_{max} \quad j = 0, \dots, N-1 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where Q , R , and Q_f are weighting matrices. According to a receding horizon approach, only the first control action in the N -step sequence is applied to the plant. Both nonlinear optimization problems (4) and (5) are here solved in Python by using IPOPT with standard options.

The controller's performance depends on how well the data-driven model captures the system dynamics. The proposed RNN-MPC formulation adopts an RNN model given by:

$$\hat{y}_k = f_{RNN}(\phi_k) \quad (6)$$

with $\phi_k := y_{k-L_b}, u_{k-L_b}, \dots, y_{k-1}, u_{k-1}$, and L_b is the look-back, that is, the number of past time steps the RNN considers to predict the plant output at time k . To incorporate the RNN model into the MPC formulation, the model dynamics is replaced by Eq. (6). Key points to note are:

- RNN-MPC formulations require previous inputs u_{k-i-1} and outputs y_{k-i-1} for $i > 0$ unlike standard MPC;
- the RNN model makes the optimization problem non-convex, leading solvers to typically converge to local minima rather than global ones.

III. THE CASE STUDY

The considered nonlinear case study comprises a CSTR with a series of two equilibrium first-order reactions.

A. System definition

The reaction scheme adopted follows: $A \xrightleftharpoons[k_4]{k_1} R \xrightleftharpoons[k_3]{k_2} S$ where A is the feed species, R is the intermediate and desired product, and S is the undesired by-product; $k_{j \in \{1,2,3,4\}}$ are the rate constants for the corresponding reaction [14]. The system dynamics in Eq. (7)-(9) are represented by highly nonlinear equations using normalized dimensionless quantities, where $C_{i \in \{A,R,S\}}$ denotes the species concentration in the reactor, C_{A0} is the feed concentration of A ; $q = \frac{Q}{V}$ is the ratio between the feed flow rate to the tank volume.

$$\frac{dC_A}{dt} = q(C_{A0} - C_A) - k_1 C_A + k_4 C_R \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC_R}{dt} &= q(1 - C_{A0} - C_R) + k_1 C_A + \\ & k_3(1 - C_A - C_R) - (k_2 + k_4)C_R \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$k_j = k_{0,j} \exp \left[\left(-\frac{E}{RT_0} \right)_j \left(\frac{1}{T} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

TABLE I
KINETICS PARAMETERS FOR THE CSTR.

	k_1	k_2	k_3	k_4
k_0	1.0	0.7	0.1	0.006
$\frac{E}{RT_0}$	8.33	10.0	50.0	83.3

Fig. 1. Input design for model training and testing stages.

For each rate constant k , $k_{0j \in \{1,2,3,4\}}$ is its Arrhenius pre-exponential constant, and $\frac{E}{RT_0}$ its normalized activation energy. The reactions are first-order and reversible, and perfect mixing is assumed; all reactor concentrations are measured. The manipulated variables (MV) are T and q , and both are also measured. The controlled variables (CV) are C_A and C_R , while C_{A0} serves as a disturbance variable. Only species A and R enter the CSTR, ensuring their feed concentrations sum to unity ($C_{A0} + C_{R0} = 1$). C_S can thus be computed over time by difference ($C_A + C_R + C_S = 1$). C_{A0} is fixed at 0.8, while values for k_0 and $\frac{E}{RT_0}$ are provided in Table I. The sampling time T_s is set at 0.1 minutes.

B. Data Generation

The CSTR numerical model is implemented in Python with its dynamics integrated using explicit Runge-Kutta method of order 5(4) via the `scipy.integrate.solve_ivp` function. To obtain data enough informative for the considered nonlinear system, the two inputs are perturbed with ramp signals, where each ramp has a randomly generated slope and duration within a specified range, bounded by a specified minimum and maximum (see Figure 1). Note that inputs are kept constant during each sampling time while system dynamics are integrated.

C. Model Definition

Five different data-driven models are considered. As NNs, two well-established recurrent structures, that is, GRU and LSTM, are defined using the Python Keras library with TensorFlow backend. As linear models, a state-space and an ARMAX model are derived for comparison using SIPPY [15], an open-source package for systems identification and validation. Finally, the “nominal” first-principles model based on the original nonlinear ODEs (7)-(9) is also investigated. White noise signals with zero mean and standard deviation of 0.004 were added to plant outputs to limit over-fitting effects. As the models were identified using different Python packages, the model parameters were extracted and implemented within CasADi [16] for a fair comparison.

Training of both types of NNs was conducted using the Adam optimizer and concluded when the loss function, defined as the mean squared error (MSE) between the true output and model output, stopped decreasing for a predefined number of epochs (i.e., `patience = 10`), or when the maximum number of epochs (150) was reached. For the first condition, a custom `Callback` was employed and evaluated at the end of each epoch. Various candidate models were developed by adjusting the number of neurons, the number of layers, and activation functions, to achieve an accurate, yet computationally efficient structure to compete with simpler linear data-driven models. Finally, in addition to the standard input, dropout, and dense layers, the optimal NNs consisted of one hidden layer with 35 neurons.

The linear state-space model was identified using the established PARSIM-K subspace method. Akaike’s information criterion (AIC) was instead employed for the model order selection, within the range [2, 10]; the optimal number of states proved to be 3. For the ARMAX model, the order was determined via a simple trial-and-error approach, optimizing MSE on outputs. Finally, the input-output model was converted into a 4-state form with the `scipy.signal.tf2ss` function.

After optimizing both GRU and LSTM NNs, they were compared to select the most suitable one for the case study. Since MSE was used as the training loss function, it was also used as basis for this comparison. The results indicated a sensible advantage for the GRU model, which demonstrated a 5% reduction in MSE error in both training and testing datasets. Additionally, the GRU model showed faster computation times (-20%) compared to LSTM, due to its simpler internal structure with 3 gates, contrasting the 4 gates in LSTM cells. Therefore, the GRU emerged as the optimal choice among RNN models for the selected case study and was used for further comparisons with alternative data-driven models.

D. Model Training and Testing

Preliminary simulations were conducted to evaluate the quality of selected models. Firstly, identified models were assessed using the same inputs of the training phase; subsequently, different inputs were employed for the testing phase

Fig. 2. Model training and testing: original vs. model output time trends.

	GRU-NN	PARSIM-K SS	ARMAX
Training	0.961	0.964	0.959
Testing	0.959	0.954	0.953

(see Fig. 2). For the final comparison, the Explained Variance (EV) metric was used:

$$EV = 100 \times \left(1 - \frac{MSE}{\sigma_y^2} \right) \quad (10)$$

where σ_y^2 is the variance of true output. Resulting numerical values of EV are shown in Table II. GRU-NN demonstrates high performance both in the training and testing stages, affirming the model's validity. Note that good performance is also observed for different network configurations, varying the number of neurons, layers, and activation functions. ARMAX and SS models just prove slightly lower in the testing stage, indicating a minor prediction capability. Despite having different numbers of linear states (4 for the ARMAX-based and 3

TABLE III
CONTROL SCENARIOS.

	C_A	C_R	T	q
Case I: Start-up	0.692	0.287	0.800	0.800
Case II: Upset recovery	0.822	0.152	1.100	0.800
Optimal set-point	0.455	0.368	0.964	1.050

for the PARSIM-K SS), they prove to perform very similarly. Therefore, for simplicity, only the SS model is adopted for further analysis.

IV. CLOSED-LOOP SIMULATIONS

Closed-loop simulations were conducted to evaluate the quality of MPCs designed on the various models (results were obtained on a MacBook Pro equipped with Intel Core i5 dual-core, 2.3 GHz, 16 GB RAM).

A. Control scenarios

Two different initial conditions were selected, with the corresponding input/output values shown in the first two rows of Table III. These conditions, named Case I and Case II, represent a reactor start-up and an upset recovery scenario, respectively. In Case I, the system is assumed to be at a low-temperature initial state with a relatively low product concentration; Case II is a high-temperature and low-yield scenario. Output noise signals with zero mean and standard deviation of 1×10^{-4} are included in the subsequent simulations.

Two standard metrics, that is, the Integral Square Error (ISE) and the Total Variation (TV) of the control action u , are selected as key performance indicators:

$$ISE = \sum_{k=0}^{N_s-1} e_k^2 T_s; \quad TV = \sum_{k=0}^{N_s-1} |u_k - u_{k-1}| \quad (11)$$

where N_s is the simulation data length and $e_k = y_{sp,k} - y_k$ is the control error signal.

All the considered MPCs adopt the same bounds for inputs, outputs, and objective functions (see Problems (4) and (5)) with the same tuning parameters: $u_{min} = [0.50, 0.40]$, $u_{max} = [1.05, 1.10]$, $y_{min} = [0.0, 0.0]$, $y_{max} = [1.0, 1.0]$; $Q_s = Q = Q_f = 17 \times I_2$, $R = [2, 0; 0, 1]$, $N = 4$, $K = 1$.

B. Optimal setpoint

In Figure 3, a comparative analysis between the various MPCs is shown for Case I and II, moving to a so-called "optimal set-point". It can be observed that the trajectories obtained with the three models are different in transient time, as the adopted tuning is the same. Nevertheless, after a few samples, they all effectively converge to the setpoint for both starting points. This result highlights the robustness and versatility of both data-driven MPCs in accommodating different initial conditions and achieving the control objectives. Only simulations as in Case I are presented in the following sections for brevity. Nevertheless, for a more comprehensive evaluation, similar simulations were run also for Case II.

Fig. 3. Optimal set-point tracking (Case I and Case II).

C. Setpoint tracking

To further assess the performance of different MPCs, a series of simulations were carried out to evaluate their response to step changes in the setpoints. Figure 4 shows the results for 4 distinct setpoint levels, comprising both upward and downward variations with the following scheme:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t \leq 20 & : C_{A,sp} = 0.601, C_{R,sp} = 0.336 \\
 20 < t \leq 40 & : C_{A,sp} = 0.660, C_{R,sp} = 0.306 \\
 40 < t \leq 60 & : C_{A,sp} = 0.527, C_{R,sp} = 0.357 \\
 t > 60 & : C_{A,sp} = 0.471, C_{R,sp} = 0.364
 \end{aligned}$$

where t is in minutes. As observed, RNN-MPC demonstrates reliable performance in achieving the various setpoints, exhibiting tight control and fast convergence to the 2nd and 4th desired values, in particular. However, for the 1st and 3rd setpoint, SS-MPC proves to outperform RNN-MPC. Nevertheless, the overall performances of both controllers are comparable for the different setpoints. The quantitative analysis, reflected in ISE and TV indicators (see Table IV), support this general observation. The RNN-MPC is comparable to the SS-MPC across different setpoints, indicating its efficacy in controlling the system dynamics and tracking setpoint variations with precision and accuracy. However, the SS model remains faster in terms of computation time, while the RNN-MPC still demonstrates higher velocity than the nominal case.

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE INDICES IN CL SIMULATIONS FOR SETPOINT VARIATIONS.

	Nominal	RNN	SS
$ISE(C_A) \times 10^2$	4.34	8.12	6.95
$ISE(C_R) \times 10^2$	0.93	1.37	1.88
$TV(T)$	1.16	2.25	1.41
$TV(q)$	1.84	0.91	1.67
MPC iteration time [ms]			
Mean	0.38	0.11	0.06
Std Dev	0.15	0.03	0.01
Max	1.13	0.33	0.17

Fig. 4. Time trends for different set-point tracking.

D. Disturbance rejection

Further simulations were conducted to assess the disturbance rejection capabilities of different MPCs. Specifically, the focus was on the response to load changes in the feed concentration of species A . Two step-wise disturbances of equal amplitude and opposite direction were introduced to reveal the system's nonlinearity, according to the following scheme: for $t \leq 5$, $C_{A0} = 0.800$; for $5 < t \leq 20$, $C_{A0} = 0.803$; for $t > 20$, $C_{A0} = 0.797$. Figure 5 presents the results: minimal disturbances in C_{A0} lead to significant variations in the steady-state values of both MVs, especially in flow rate q . Two data-driven MPCs exhibit a different performance in transient time, with the RNN-MPC showing a slower behavior compared to the SS-MPC. Nevertheless, both models demonstrate acceptable proficiency in rejecting disturbances,

Fig. 5. Time trends in disturbance rejection.

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE INDICES IN CL FOR DISTURBANCE REJECTION.

	Nominal	RNN	SS
$ISE(C_A) \times 10^3$	0.01	9.61	8.79
$ISE(C_R) \times 10^3$	0.01	2.24	4.16
$TV(T)$	0.37	1.75	0.76
$TV(q)$	3.85	0.78	0.63
MPC iteration time [ms]			
Mean	0.28	0.10	0.07
Std Dev	0.04	0.03	0.02
Max	0.55	0.39	0.29

highlighting their effectiveness in ensuring system stability. Table V further supports these observations; note that since the variations in two species concentrations are negligible, ISE values are minimal. Confirmations also arise from the comparison of the computational times.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the integration of established RNNs with MPC for complex nonlinear systems. In particular, a single CSTR, characterized by involved kinetics made by a series of first-order equilibrium reactions, was considered. The training dataset is generated with a first-principle model represented by ODEs and the system evolution is described by explicit Runge-Kutta 4(5) method. Compared to standard data-driven linear models, such as ARMAX and state-space

formulation, GRU and LSTM neural networks demonstrate competitive performance in the training and testing stages. To this aim, GRU-based MPC was compared with a nominal nonlinear MPC and a linear MPC based on the best state-space model previously identified. Suitable performance indicators, such as ISE and TV of inputs, showcase the effectiveness of the RNN-based MPC in tracking setpoints and rejecting disturbances. Despite its higher computational times, the RNN-MPC proves promising capabilities for controlling complex reaction systems with nonlinear dynamics, offering a viable alternative to traditional linear model-based approaches. Future developments will delve into leveraging the computational time of the RNN-based MPC and testing different tuning sets to optimize the performance of alternative RNN structures.

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